

Technologies of Creating Graphic Organizers in "Mindonmap" Software

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Abstract:

The article describes the internal structure of the software "MindOnMap", instructions for its use, as well as the technology of creating graphic organizers, in particular, "Mind Map" and "Concept Map".

Keywords: "Mind Maps", "MindOnMap" software, graphic organizer, graphic organizer "model".

In his address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the people of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev commented on the education system and said that improving the quality of education is the only way to develop the new Uzbekistan. they will pay special attention to the way .¹In particular, let's pay attention to the following points taken from this application: " Our children need to master their mother tongue and foreign languages thoroughly from school and learn to work on a computer ." There are computerized classrooms in schools, and if we directly refer to computer technology not only in informatics, but also in other taught subjects, especially the process of acquiring and strengthening the linguistic knowledge of the native language of the students, it will turn into an environment that encourages the use of computer technology. If we get it, we would have achieved our goal to a certain extent.

Michael Michalko, known as one of the world's most famous creativity experts, has this to say about Mind Maps: Mind Maps are a whole-brain alternative to linear thinking. It stretches in all directions and captures thoughts from every angle” [Tony Buzan, 2012; 13].

¹ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan. 2022 December 20 . <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/5774>

In fact, we are able to express the thought expressed in our brain in the form of a "map" as a kind of written representation. In this case, "Mind Maps" will help us.

Recognized as one of the top 5 speakers in the world and described as “one of the most influential leaders in the field of creative thinking” [<https://medium.com/@moustafahamwi/tony-buzan-inventor-of-mind-mapping-releases-a-volcano-of-passion-e8da34d9c5cf#:~:text=Tony%20Buzan%20is%20the%20world-renowned,get%20more%20passionate%20than%20that> !] Tony Buzan in his book " The Ultimate Book of Mind Maps " (The Best Book of Mind Maps) specifically emphasizes that "Mind Maps" look like "city maps" [Tony Buzan, 2012; 15].

<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 2</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">A view of the "Mind Map" proposed by Tony Buzan (see Figure 1.)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">City map. It is similar in form to the "Mind Map" proposed by Tony Buzan. (See Figure 2.)</p>

Just like the most central part of the city, these "Mind Maps" have the same "central node" and the rest of the directions begin to appear as "suggestions" in the process of thinking from the center. Representation of large amounts of information using "Mind Maps" makes it possible to collect them in one place. Students will also be able to express a unique form of visualization in the process of creating this type of map. So, this type of graphic organizer appears, first of all, as an educational tool that exhibits a unique visuality.

In the sources of mother tongue teaching methods, "Mind maps" are also found as "Perception maps". For example, in the textbooks called "Educational technologies" by Sh.S. Shoyimova and others, there are "Mind map", "Intellect-map", "Mental map", "Perception map", "Thinking map" [Shoyimova Sh.S. et al., 2020; 250] we can see that it is called by such names.

We have the opportunity to create graphic organizers online in MindOnMap software. To create this type of graphic organizer, we must first visit this site: <https://www.mindonmap.com/uz/> . As a result, the following window will appear (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. MindOnMap software window

First, we need to know more about this program. After entering through the specified link, we will see sections such as "Products", "Diagrams", "Tutorial", "TSS", "Blog". possible (see Fig. 4.). We enter the section called "Tutorial".

Figure 4. The name of the sections in MindOnMap

In this part, you will start working with this program, creating the graphic organizers you need for yourself. The first step is to add a node (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. A guide to adding the desired "node" in MindOnMap

You can get complete and detailed information about all the practical work related to creating a graphic organizer in the section called "Guide". While many graphic organizer software are reviewed in English, the convenience aspect of this software is that the instructions for its use are provided in Uzbek.

Now we need to get into this program. To do this, we need to select "Login" located at the top of the screen (see Figure 6).

Figure 6.

We will need to fill in the blanks, namely the fields called "Email" and "Password" (see Figure 7).

Figure 7.

If you haven't registered with this software before, just hover your mouse cursor over the blue "Create it" text and right-click.

After filling in the necessary fields, the "Sign up" command is selected (see Fig. 8).

Figure 8.

Then a window with the following appearance will be created (see Fig. 9).

Figure 9.

You will receive a "notification" that you have registered, that a confirmation message has been sent to the email address you entered, that you need to confirm to use the benefits of this letter, and the "Done" command will be selected.

We can even create "Concept Maps" with this software. To do this, we go to the section called "Personal use" from the section "Diagrams" and select the place called "Concept map" (see Figure 10).

Figure 10.

After entering this section, you will notice the following sub-sections.

1. Concept map creator (see Figure 11).

Figure 11.

In this section, you can create a free concept map online. To do this, you need to select the part called "Conception" shown in the picture. If you enter here, the following window will open (see Figure 12).

Figure 12.

To create a "concept map" we select the "New" command (see Fig. 13).

Figure 13.

Move the cursor to "Mind map" and click the left mouse button. As a result, a workspace is created where you can create a Mind Map.

The inscription "Main node" located in the center can serve as the main concept in the process of creating concept maps (see Figure 14).

Figure 14.

As we create the concept map we need to create, we need to name this document. Initially, when the first workspace is created during concept mapping, it says "Untitled". This name means that the document you are creating is not named.

There are 2 different ways **to name** the document that contains the graphic organizer you are creating.

Method 1.

- a) You move the cursor over the inscription "Untitled" and click the left mouse button;
- b) You name the concept map you are creating.

Method 2.

- a) You hover over the right-facing arrow in front of Untitled and click the left mouse button. You will see the following window appear (see Figure 15).

Figure 15.

- b) From this window, select the command called "Rename". Then this window is created (see Fig. 16).

Figure 16.

- c) In the section called "Please Enter the name" - "Please enter the name", you write the name of the document you can create and select the "Ok" command. As a result, this file will be saved and named with the name you entered.

On page 29 of the 6th grade mother tongue textbook created on the basis of the national curriculum [Azimova I., Mavlonova K. et al., 2022; 29] Under the theme of "Amir", the task of writing the highlighted words in the given text into word groups was requested based on the table provided as an example. But we will start this task by creating a graphic organizer model online in MindOnMap software. As a result, we create the following graphic organizer model (see Fig. 17).

Figure 17.

The use of a graphic organizer called "Mind Maps" is very effective for us when analyzing texts.

In this way, we develop students' morphological knowledge. That is, students indicate to which word group the highlighted words in the text belong through a graphic organizer that is considered their "creative drawing". That is, during the creation of this "Mind Map", a "main node" is initially placed at the central point. We can label it as 'phrases'. From the "central node" we write down the names of nouns, adjectives, numbers, verbs and pronouns. From the words highlighted in the text, those belonging to the noun group (*vein, Bukhara, official*), adjectives (*ill, young, burro*), verbs We place the words (*ranjibdi, debdi, jazz kirifdi*), the number word group (*three*), the pronoun word group (*he, this, you*) in this map. If you notice, we used different shapes and colors for each word group . What are the words *tomir* , *official* ? the answer to the question is that it is coming as a kindred horse, and where is *Bukhara* ? as an answer to the question, it comes as a toponym, indicating the name of the place. Since all of them belong to the noun group, the following form color are usefully used. Shapes and colors that belong to other word groups have been chosen to encourage the development of students' ability to distinguish colors by working with shapes and colors using the MindOnMap software.

On pages 30-31 of the 6th grade mother tongue textbook, there is a text called "The Home of the Reserve Army", and we will create a model of the "Mind Map" corresponding to this text as follows (see Figure 18).

Figure 18.

We can say the following conclusions about this MindOnMap online software:

1. It has a convenient design and is easy to use.
2. We will be able to easily convert the generated graphic organizers into various convenient formats: jpg, png, svg, pdf, doc.
3. We will be able to distribute the resulting graphic organizers through social networks or print them from a printer on paper, and we will be able to find this graphic organizer through the provided link.
4. We will only be able to use this software online.

List of used literature:

1. Azimova I., Mavlonova K. et al. Mother tongue: textbook for 6th grade. - Tashkent: Republican Education Center, 2022. - 224 p.
2. <https://medium.com/@moustafahamwi/tony-buzan-inventor-of-mind-mapping-releases-a-volcano-of-passion-e8da34d9c5cf#:~:text=Tony%20Buzan%20is%20the%20world-renowned,get%20more%20passionate%20than%20that> !
3. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Контекстное_меню
4. Shoyimova Sh.S., Khoshimova KM, Mirzayeva Sh.R., Koziboyeva MM Educational technologies: textbook. - Tashkent: Ijod-print, 2020. - 310 p.
5. Tony Buzan. The Ultimate Book of Mind Maps . -Epub: 2012, August. ISBN: 9780007499564. – 218 p.
6. Nabijanov Yusufjon ugli Inomiddin. (2023). Graphic Organizers as a Tool for Ensuring the Effectiveness of Innovative Educational Technologies. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 29–39. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1234>